

GMPI: Global Myocardial Performance Index.

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Provisional Results of Original Research

A new echocardiographic index has been developed that is easily determined and represents global LV function, incorporating both systolic and diastolic components. The ROC analysis below demonstrates the index's sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing heart failure, compared to EF in the same population.

Provisional findings from this research confirm a highly significant predictive value of the index for heart failure, heart failure mortality, cardiovascular mortality, and overall mortality. Notably, the correlations of this index are more significant than those of EF.

The index demonstrates significant capability for the early detection of heart failure

Area Under the ROC Curve

Test Result Variable(s)	Area
GMP-index	.839
EF	.283

